

DYNAMICS OF POPULATION IN DEMOGRAPHY AND ITS ABSOLUTE INDICATORS.

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Annotation: *This article covers the dynamics of the population number, the identification of the population using formulas, the use of statistical data, the birth, the natural increase of the population, the processes of immigration emigration of the population.*

Key words: *continent, administrative border, statistical source, birth, population number, Death, growth coefficient, population dynamics, immigrants, immigrants, natural growth.*

The number of inhabitants represents the amount of inhabitants of a ma'ium region (globe, continent, State, province, district, territory, settlement). For example, in 2017, the population of the globe was 7,5 billion, the population of the African continent was 1250 million, and the population of Uzbekistan was 32.5 million. When calculating the number of inhabitants, the borders of ma' Muri for the O'trak population and areals for the nomadic population are taken as the basis. In demography, the number of inhabitants is the most general basic indicator, which means the amount of population in a certain period of time. In statistical sources, the number of inhabitants mium is brought to a date (1 January, 1 July or 31 December). For example, the population of Uzbekistan in 1991 amounted to 20708.2 thousand in Yanvar, in 2000-1 Yanvar-24487.7 thousand, in 2017-1 Yanvar-32120.5 thousand. This indicator can not be taken for the whole year, because during the year, that is, from 1 janvar to 31 December, the number of inhabitants varies regularly on the account of birth and death. The change in the number of population

of the region or state under study in the mium period (2 years, 5, 10, 15 and more years) is reflected in the dynamics of the population. The dynamics of the population is expressed in such indicators as its total, total (absolute) number, growth coefficient, growth rate of the population. When each region studies the number of inhabitants, as noted above. it is divided into permanent (registered Permanently in the same territory) and real (Living for a certain period of time in the same territory in the investigated period) population. In carrying out Demographic Research, the number of the theoretical population, as well as the existing, real population, is used. The theoretical population number is an invariable-stable population number. The stable population is derived from the Latin word *stabilis*, which means permanent, unchangeable. The main category of the population is the existing population. When calculating the demographic coefficients, the available population is used. It is also used in the study of the absolute number of the population for the period between - lists of the available population. The absolute number of the population varies regularly on the basis of its natural and mechanical action. If the population increases in terms of periods, the changes in the dynamics of the absolute number of the population will be positive, if decreasing, it will have a negative feature. For example, the dynamics of population in the state of Uzbekistan has been regularly increasing in 1926-2009. Hence, the dynamics of the population was characterized by a positive feature. But in the Second World War (1941 - 1945 years), the number of the population decreased for some time and a negative situation was observed in the dynamics of the population. The total absolute (absolute) number of the population is a quantitative expression of a person in a certain territory or population group at a certain time. The absolute number of the population in the population science research, as a key indicator, provides information about the number of the population on a specific date. Changes in the absolute number of the population are determined by the coefficient of growth. In determining the absolute growth coefficient of the population, the following formula is used:

$$A_{to} = P_i - P_o, \text{ such}$$

A_{to} - absolute (absolute growth) growth.

P₀ - population at the beginning of the period under study.

P_i - population at the end of the period under study.

For example, we determine the absolute growth of the population of Uzbekistan in 1991 - 2009 using the above formula.

$P_0 = 1991 - 20,7$ million $P_i = 2008 - 27,6$ million $A_{to} = 1991 - 2009 - 27,6 - 20,7 = 6,9$ that is to say, the absolute growth of the population of Uzbekistan in 1991 - 2009 amounted to 6.9 million people, or during the recorded period, the population of the Republic increased to 6.9 million people. It is known that the population of the state or territory will increase on account of the birth and the arrival of the immigrant, while on account of death and the departure of the emigrant will decrease.

So, the indicator of the absolute number of the population consists of 4 components:

- 1) number of births;
- 2) number of dead;
- 3) number of immigrants;
- 4) the number of immigrants.

The concept of "balance" is also used in the study of changes in the population. The balance of birth and death is the natural growth of the population (the difference in the number of births and deaths in a given period). The balance of immigrants and emigrants is the mechanical growth of the population. If external migration is not a closed population, then in the presence of external migration, on the contrary, it is called an open population. The natural growth of the population and the balance of migration are components of population change over a certain period of time. The most accurate information about the absolute number of inhabitants is obtained by conducting a population census. And the population list can be found in certain periods (5, 10, 15, etc.).k.years). The demographic balance method is used in determining the number of population in the population list range.

This method is expressed in the demographic equilibrium equation:

$$P_i = P_0 + (B-D) + (M_i - M_o), \text{ such}$$

P₀ - population (beginning of the period under study);

B - number of births in the period under study;

D - number of deaths in the period under study;

M_i - number of arrivals (immigrants)

M_o - number of arrivals (migrants) ;

We determine the absolute number of the population of Uzbekistan in 1 January 2001 using the above equation. In 2000, 1 January (R_0) the population of the Republic was 24582.8 people. In the period from 1 January to 31 December 2000, 527580 babies (N) were born, 135598 people lost their lives (M). During this period, the number of arrivals to the Republic (M_i) amounted to 145880 people, while the number of departures (D) amounted to 212472 people. So, $P_{2001}=24582,8+(527580-135598)+(145880-212472)=24908,2$;
 $P_{2001}=24908,212$.

There are specific disadvantages of determining changes in the dynamics of the population on absolute indicators. The longer the period under study, the lower the accuracy of changes in population numbers. Also, the features of the middle periodontium remain completely unopened. In this regard, it is desirable to determine the change in population by relative indicators. In Bunda, the period under study is divided into several small-to-small periods, in which population growth is determined relative. Davriy and average annual growth coefficients of the population also serve in the scientific implementation of the population dynamics.

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